

STRUCTURAL DECOMPOSITION AND INSTABILITY ANALYSIS OF SERICULTURE GROWTH IN ASSAM STATE

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Abstract

Sericulture is one of the important and significant sectors for the rural economy and contributes in poverty alleviation through employment generation and income all round the year to the rural farm families in India. The present study undertaken in state of Assam with aim of the relative contribution of area and yield on production and instability index for sericulture (Eri, Muga and Mulberry) by using time series data relating to area and production of cocoon and raw silk for the time period from 2001-02 to 2015-16. The findings reveals that the change in production can be mainly attributed due to yield effect rather than area expansion under Eri, Muga and Mulberry in selected districts for the study period. Instability Index of area under Eri (29.94%) and Muga (20.62%) was recorded low however, high for mulberry (38.24%). Instability in Eri (20.62%) and Muga (10.42%) cocoon production was found to be low while it was recorded high for mulberry (59.56%) whereas, instability in silk production for Eri (23.35%) and Muga (7.90%) was found to be low but high for mulberry (39.92%) in Assam state.

Keywords: Sericulture, area, production, productivity, decomposition analysis and instability index.

Introduction

The word sericulture has been derived from the Greek word 'sericos' which means 'silk' and the English word "culture" means 'rearing'. Sericulture is the art and science of rearing of silkworms for the production of raw silk and its end product is silk. Silk is referred as "Queen of fabrics" and is well known for its natural colour, purity and unusual lustre. It is natural fabric, animal oriented and produced from silkworm (Hiware 2012). Sericulture refers to conscious mass-scale rearing of silk producing organisms in order to obtain silk from them (Ganga 2006).

Sericulture involves cultivation of food plants, production of silkworm eggs, rearing of silkworm by feeding them the leaves of the food plants to obtain cocoon and yarn from the cocoon by reeling or spinning. There are four major varieties of silk namely, Mulberry, Eri, Muga and Tasar, each of which is produced by a distinct variety of silkworm feeding on a specific host plant. It is practiced in a wide range of agro-climatic regions like forests, hilly areas and plains. In fact, the recent technological advancements have made it possible to practice it on an intensive scale, mainly due to increased profits obtained from it as compared to most of the crops and enterprises. Sericulture is an important labour intensive, agro-based industry providing gainful employment to unemployed/underemployed in the rural and semi-urban areas and facilitates economic development and improvement in the standard of life of the people. Therefore, it has turned out to be a highly remunerative cash crop with minimum investment and high dividends (Bhat and Choure, 2014).

According to International Sericultural Commission (ISC) 2016-17, the total raw silk production during 2016-17 was about 192692.5 MT. China is the leading producer of silk in the world with 158400 MT and accounting for 80 per cent of the world's silk output. In India, silk production has increased from 26480 MT in 2013-14 to 30348 MT in 2016-17 with 17.70 per cent of the world's silk output and stands as second largest producer of silk.

Sericulture stands next to agriculture for rural employment in India. It becomes a matter of priority to examine the sericulture production trend over the years and reasons for growth fluctuation. Whether, the fluctuation is statistically normal or is under the influence of some of the factors getting changed due to one or the other reason of temporary or permanent nature (Rai and Dwivedi, 2015). Still the domestic demand is not fulfilled within the nation. Out of the annual raw silk production; there exists a huge domestic demand as the consumption rate is highly elastic. This has resulted in creating a larger gap in production and consumption of silk products (Bhat and Choure, 2014). Hence the present study carried out decomposition and instability analysis in sericulture growth in the state of Assam.

Methodology

The present study was conducted in Assam and its major sericulture prominent districts like Karbi-Anglong, N.C. Hills, Lakhimpur, Sivasagar, Golaghat, Dhemaji and Dibrugarh. The study was entirely based on secondary data collected for all the districts of Assam from different published sources such as Statistical Handbook of Assam, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Guwahati and Annual Reports of Central Silk Board (CSB), Bangalore. Secondary data relating to area and production of cocoon and raw silk of Eri, Muga and mulberry for the period from 2001-02 to 2015-16 was collected and analysed.

Decomposition analysis

Decomposition can be used to see the change in total production. The total change in production is decomposed into three effects i.e., area effect (% contribution of area), yield effect (% contribution of yield) and interaction effect (% contribution of interaction). The contribution of area is the part of production due to additional area with the base year average yield, the contribution of average yield is the part of production due to additional yield with base year area and the contribution of the interaction is the part of production jointly due to additional yield and additional area (Sharma and Subramanyam, 1984). These three effects were studied on change in cocoon production of Eri, Muga and Mulberry. This is elaborated as below: Let P_o and P_n be production in base year and nth year.

$$P_o = A_o \cdot Y_o \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$P_n = A_n \cdot Y_n$$

Where A_o , A_n represent area Y_o , Y_n represent yield for the base year and nth year, respectively. The base year and nth year observations are triennium averages.

$$P_n - P_o = \Delta P$$

$$A_n - A_o = \Delta A \dots\dots\dots 2$$

$$Y_n - Y_o = \Delta Y$$

From 1 and 2 we can write

$$P_o + \Delta P = (A_o + \Delta A) (Y_o + \Delta Y)$$

$$\Delta P = (A_o + \Delta A) (Y_o + \Delta Y) - P_o$$

$$= (A_o + \Delta A) (Y_o + \Delta Y) - A_o \cdot Y_o$$

$$= (A_o \cdot Y_o + \Delta A Y_o + \Delta Y A_o + \Delta A \Delta Y - A_o \cdot Y_o)$$

$$\Delta P = \Delta A Y_o + \Delta Y A_o + \Delta A \Delta Y$$

Where,

$$\Delta P = \text{Change in production}$$

$$\Delta A y_o = \text{Area effect}$$

$$\Delta Y a_o = \text{Yield effect}$$

$$\Delta A \Delta Y = \text{Interaction effect}$$

Thus, total change in production is decomposed into three effects viz. area effect, yield effect and interaction effect.

Coefficient of Variation

A Coefficient of Variation (CV) is a statistical measure of the dispersion of data points in a data series around the mean. The

coefficient of variation represents the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean, and it is a useful statistic for comparing the degree of variation from one data series to another. It is calculated by using following formula:

$$CV = \left(\frac{\sigma}{\mu} \right) \times 100$$

Where,

σ = Standard deviation

μ = Mean

Instability Index

The Cuddy-Della Valle index was used as a measure of instability for sericulture growth. The instability for the area, cocoon production and raw silk production of Eri, Muga and Mulberry in Assam were calculated for prominent districts and state level. The simple coefficient of variation overestimates the level of instability in time series data characterized by long term trends whereas the Cuddy-Della Valle index corrects the coefficient of variation by taking into consideration the coefficient of determination (Cuddy and Della Valle 1978).

The instability index (IX), is given by the expression:

$$CD = CV * (1 - R^2)^{1/2}$$

Where,

CD = Cuddy-Della Valle index

CV = Coefficient of variation and is equal to standard deviation / mean

R² = Coefficient of determination from a time trend regression adjusted by the number of degrees of freedom

Results and Discussions

Decomposition analysis of Eri, Muga and Mulberry of Assam

The Decomposition analysis of Eri, Muga and Mulberry of Assam was tabulated in the table 1, 2 and 3. The findings shows that change in the production of Eri in the state was recorded at 3286.75 MT, as shown in the Table 1 mainly due to yield effect (61.97%) rather than area expansion. Among the districts, the highest contribution of area effect was found for Dhemaji district with 93.59 percent. On other hand yield effect was found to be highest in N.C. Hills district with 138.99 percent followed by Sivasagar district (109.53%) and the highest change in production and interaction effect of Eri was recorded for Karbi-Anglong district with 1669.97 MT and 86.99 percent respectively. However, Dhemaji and Sivasagar saw change in production mainly because of area expansion and yield effect respectively (Table 1).

The Muga production in the state increased by 1229.73 MT because of yield effect with 54.38 per cent rather than area expansion. Amongst the districts the production was highest for Sivasagar district with 301.79 MT with yield effect of 172.37 percent followed by Lakhimpur district with 195.89 MT with yield effect of 119.88 percent however, N C Hills having the high interaction effect with 65.33 percent (Table 2).

The mulberry production in Assam state increased to the tune of 2605.93 MT because of relative contribution of yield was greater than area at 119.46 percent (Table 3). Regarding the same for the districts, majority of the districts showed change in production due to effect of yield. The maximum contribution of yield effect to change in production was found for the selected districts than area and interaction effect barring Dhemaji. The highest change in production observed for Dhemaji district at 867.95 MT due to interaction effect at 97.55 percent.

Instability in area under Eri, Muga and Mulberry at state and district level

The instability in area under Eri, Muga and Mulberry in Assam and the districts in terms of CV and IX. As observed in the Table 4, CV and IX were 30.90 and 29.94 per cent respectively for Assam. Among the districts, highest instability in area under eri was observed for Karbi Anglong district with CV of 175.45 and IX of

182.06 per cent respectively. The lowest instability in area under eri was recorded for N.C. Hills district (CV 20.78% and IX 20.64%).

The instability in area under Muga, for the state as a whole is lower than eri with CV of 23.83 per cent and IX of 20.62 per cent respectively. Among the districts, the highest CV (83.38%) and IX (67.28%) were noticed in N.C. Hills district indicating high instability in area under Muga in the district. Lowest instability in area under Muga was observed for Dhemaj (CV 24.06% and IX 21.10%).

Instability in area under mulberry for the state as a whole was found to be high with CV of 36.90 and IX of 38.24 per cent, respectively. District wise analysis revealed that Lakhimpur district showed the highest CV (62.03) and IX (62.14%) amongst all the districts and Karbi Anglong district recorded lowest CV (21.04%) and IX (21.33). Thus, high instability in area under mulberry was observed for Lakhimpur and lowest for Karbi Anglong district.

Instability in cocoon production of Eri, Muga and Mulberry at state and district level

Table 5 shows instability in cocoon production of eri, muga and mulberry in Assam and the districts in terms of CV and IX. It is observed from the Table that CV and IX were 60.57 and 20.62 per cent respectively for Assam. Among the districts, highest instability in Eri cocoon production was observed for Golaghat district with CV of 105.99 and IX of 65.39 per cent respectively. The lowest instability in Eri cocoon production was recorded for Karbi Anlong district with CV of 46.99 and IX of 46.01 per cent respectively. In terms of IX, instability in Eri cocoon production was also found to be low for Sivasagar district (17.35%).

In case of production of Muga cocoons, CV and IX were 17.04 and 10.42 per cent for the state of Assam indicating low instability in Muga cocoon production compare to Eri and mulberry. Among the districts, Dhemaji (CV 31.37% & IX 29.03%) showed lowest instability in Muga cocoon production among all the districts of Assam. Karbi-Anglong (CV 182.34% & IX 79.32%) recorded the highest instability in Muga cocoon production.

As regards to instability in mulberry cocoon production, it is observed from the Table 5 that instability in mulberry cocoon production for the state as a whole was high as compared to Muga cocoon production with CV of 78.61 per cent and IX of 59.56 per cent respectively. Among the districts, the highest CV (115.52%) and IX (105.77%) were noticed in N. C. Hills district indicating high instability in mulberry cocoon production in the district. Lowest instability in mulberry cocoon production was observed for Lakhimpur district with CV of 49.72 per cent and IX of 35.57 per cent respectively.

Instability in raw silk production of Eri, Muga and Mulberry at state and district level

Table 6 shows instability in raw silk production of Eri, Muga and Mulberry in Assam and the districts in terms of CV and IX. It is observed from the table that, CV and IX were 71.67 and 23.35 per cent respectively for Assam. Among the districts, highest instability in eri silk production was observed for Goalaghat (CV 106.39% & 69.90%). The lowest instability in eri silk production was recorded for Karbi Anglong (CV 42.34% & IX 41.60%).

In case of production of Muga silk, CV and IX were 13.85 and 7.90 per cent for the state of Assam indicating low instability in Muga silk production compared to other silks. Among the districts, Karbi Anglong (CV 178.06% & IX 77.76) showed highest instability in Muga silk production among all the districts of Assam. Dhemaji (CV 28.46% & IX 26.71%) recorded the lowest instability in Muga silk production.

As regards to instability in Mulberry silk production, it is observed from the Table 6 that instability in mulberry silk production for the state as a whole was high as compared to Muga silk production with CV of 185.32 per cent and IX of 150.25 per cent respectively. Among the districts, the highest CV (115.50%) and IX (108.99%) were noticed in the N.C. Hills district indicating high instability in Mulberry silk production in the district. Lowest instability in Mulberry silk production was observed for Sivasagar (CV 47.87% &

IX 46.98%) and Lakhimpur (CV 49.09% & IX 37.02%) district, respectively.

Table 1: District wise Contribution of area, yield and interaction effect on production of Eri in Assam from 2001-02 to 2015-16

District/State	Area Effect	Yield Effect	Interaction Effect	Change in Production
Karbi-Anglong	-2.02	15.03	86.99	1669.97
N.C. Hills	-17.05	138.99	-21.94	41.50
Lakhimpur	3.42	85.25	11.33	100.98
Sivasagar	-0.54	109.53	-8.99	358.26
Golaghat	0.23	96.70	3.08	287.01
Dhemaji	93.59	2.59	3.82	99.34
Dibrugarh	9.10	52.89	38.00	121.80
Others	-1.99	129.04	-21.79	163.51
Assam	9.00	61.97	29.03	3286.75

Table 2: District wise Contribution of area, yield and interaction effect on production of Muga in Assam from 2001-02 to 2015-16

District/State	Area Effect	Yield Effect	Interaction Effect	Change in Production
Karbi-Anglong	1.41	62.59	36	29.66
N.C. Hills	3.53	31.13	65.33	19.93
Lakhimpur	-13.35	119.88	-6.53	195.89
Sivasagar	-26.98	172.37	-45.39	301.79
Golaghat	13.25	78.78	7.97	98.57
Dhemaji	90.64	6.07	3.29	116.47
Dibrugarh	-51.54	134.82	16.72	-73.96
Others	3.66	97.99	-1.65	76.58
Assam	34.66	54.38	10.96	1229.73

Table 3: District wise Contribution of area, yield and interaction effect on production of Mulberry in Assam from 2001-02 to 2015-16

District/State	Area Effect	Yield Effect	Interaction Effect	Change in Production
Karbi-Anglong	-5.41	115.22	-9.81	12.76
N.C. Hills	3.83	81.35	14.82	7.17
Lakhimpur	1.62	92.91	5.47	38.48
Sivasagar	-6.16	136.62	-30.46	31.85
Golaghat	1.73	90.97	7.3	31.76
Dhemaji	0.2	2.25	97.55	867.95
Dibrugarh	15.03	72.07	12.9	10.08
Others	6.83	108.77	-15.60	23.82
Assam	-0.7	119.46	-18.76	2605.93

Table 4: District wise coefficient of variation (CV) and instability index (IX) of area under Eri, Muga and Mulberry of Assam for the period from 2001-02 to 2015-16

DISTRICT	ERI		MUGA		MUBERRY	
	CV	IX	CV	IX	CV	IX
Karbi-Anglong	175.45	182.06	38.01	34.04	21.04	21.33
N.C. Hills	20.78	20.64	83.38	67.28	57.32	57.53
Lakhimpur	26.00	26.84	26.13	26.30	62.03	62.14
Sivasagar	32.05	32.38	31.88	31.33	43.13	42.96
Goalaghat	44.31	43.76	39.58	41.07	52.79	53.87
Dhemaji	41.95	26.96	24.06	21.10	31.36	32.30
Dibrugarh	34.30	25.33	23.30	23.89	40.08	41.14
Others	28.92	23.96	41.36	38.31	59.19	55.28
Assam	30.90	29.94	23.83	20.62	36.90	38.24

Table 5: District wise coefficient of variation (CV) and instability index (IX) of cocoon production of Eri, Muga and Mulberry of Assam for the period from 2001-02 to 2015-16

DISTRICT	ERI		MUGA		MUBERRY	
	CV	IX	CV	IX	CV	IX
Karbi-Anglong	46.99	46.01	182.34	79.32	102.10	102.11
N.C. Hills	62.51	58.79	174.2	83.80	115.52	105.77
Lakhimpur	82.13	55.11	38.34	38.26	49.72	35.37

Sivasagar	47.87	17.35	44.27	45.06	56.41	47.87
Goalaghat	105.99	69.39	41.53	39.51	65.15	61.56
Dhemaji	77.64	64.23	31.37	29.03	75.58	53.78
Dibrugarh	84.83	32.48	70.71	71.06	52.38	47.76
Others	85.45	62.17	89.98	59.72	90.91	82.61
Assam	60.57	20.62	17.04	10.42	78.61	59.56

Table 6: District wise coefficient of variation (CV) and instability index (IX) of raw silk production in Eri, Muga and Mulberry of Assam for the period from 2001-02 to 2015-16

DISTRICT	ERI		MUGA		MUBERRY	
	CV	IX	CV	IX	CV	IX
Karbi-Anglong	42.34	41.6	178.06	77.76	98.91	101.87
N.C. Hills	63.65	60.79	176	84.26	115.5	108.99
Lakhimpur	85.62	56.49	41.94	34.43	49.09	37.02
Sivasagar	100.54	35.90	52.60	54.23	47.87	46.98
Goalaghat	106.39	69.90	39.03	37.38	71.9	73.37
Dhemaji	78.12	62.98	28.46	26.71	74.34	56.17
Dibrugarh	92.99	61.53	72.88	73.44	48.55	47.72
Others	89.48	59.19	85.79	63.46	97.01	87.54
Assam	71.67	23.35	13.85	7.90	185.32	150.25

Conclusion

Improvement in the sericulture activities in Assam has been witnessed but at a very slow rate compared to traditional states like, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal. North East India has contributed significantly to India's non-mulberry raw silk production as compared to mulberry. At the state level Eri, Muga and Mulberry had an increase in production during study period. For all Eri, Muga and Mulberry the change in production can be mainly attributed due to yield effect rather than area expansion under Eri, Muga and Mulberry. Further, area and interaction effect on change in Mulberry production was negative compared to Eri and Muga. Instability was recorded high in mulberry in terms of area, production of cocoon and silk compare to non-mulberry crops like Eri and Muga in the state. Districts falling under low instability category have the most favorable situation of cultivation of the three varieties of silk. Highly instable districts should be checked for any adversity affecting the cultivation process of particular variety of silk in order to help minimize instability.

7.

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